

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF LOADING AND UNLOADING PLATFORM FOR TWO WHEELERS

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Abstract

Lift is a simple device use to raise the object from ground level to a certain height to perform a specific work with aiming of possible maximum load and minimum efforts. Lifts are generally operated either hydraulic, pneumatic or mechanical type. In many vehicle manufacturing industries, there are using lifting mechanism for loading and unloading operations which have to invest a huge capital for installing a existing bulkey and large platform which generally based on hydraulic means. This type of machine uses while export and import business. The main purpose of our study is to design and development of loading and unloading platform for two wheelers. Material selection plays important role in designing a machine and also influence on several factor such as strength, reliability, durability and resistance which leads to increase the life of lift. The aim of the project is to design and development of wire rope operated platform which lifts maximum 877.5 kg load including factor of safety with minimum time and labour for per cycle operation. Platform movement is achieved safely by using wire rope with the help of gear motor and drum assembly mechanism is of 2.8 m from the ground level. The design is performed by considering a mechanical lift as a portable, suitable for all type of load application and without any hydraulic or pneumatic means. The design is developed keeping in mind that consideration of all safety parameters. Lubrication required in few moving parts only. The aim of this paper is design, analysis and fabrication of a mechanical lift model which operate efficiently, consistently, sholud be easy to handle, multifunctional, cost effective, compact in size. Drafting and drawing of loading

and unloading mechanical lift carried out in AUTOCAD with suitable modeling. The analysis of mechanical lift includes total deformation load, reaction forces, buckling and bending failures, equivalent stresses were done in ANSYS Software. Finally this analysis of strength, toughness, elasticity and temperature distribution is carried out in order to check the coherence of the design value.

Keywords : Hydraulic, Pneumatic, Mechanism, Platform, Wire rope, Design, Lubrication, Analysis, AUTOCAD, ANSYS Software.

I. Introduction

Lifts are generally used for loading and unloading of goods, two wheeler or person. Lifts are most commonly used mode of vertical transformation in day to day life with certain height depending upon requirement. Nowadays many lifting systems are designed to used for various purposes in industry. These system can be used in multi purpose application and wide range of services such as cleaning, maintenance activities. Lifts are In existing system of loading and unloading, there is used ramp system which is considered a very risky and time consuming for loading and unloading operation. At the time of loading and unloading operation of vehicles, more than two labour and sometimes four labour are required which is uneconomically and vehicle may be damage in unbalancing condition. There will be directly influences on productivity which is integral part of any industry.

Fig 1 Design of loading & unloading platform

II. Literature Review

- 1. Miss. Aishwarya B. Shinde, et.al [1]** In this paper they have developed a concept of design and fabrication of mechanical lift for transportation. This project describes the design as well as analysis of a mechanical scissor lift which works on the principle of screw jack. The design will be developed keeping in mind that the lift can be operated by mechanical means so that the overall cost of the scissor lift is reduced. Also such design can make the lift more compact and much suitable for medium scale work. Conventionally a scissor lift or jack is used for lifting a vehicle to change a tire to gain access to go to the underside of the vehicle to lift the body to appreciable height, and many other applications.

2. **Nukul G. Tambe, et.al [2]** In this paper Mr. Tambe and his team have developed a system of loading and unloading platform for two wheelers. This deals with the design as well as analysis of a vehicle ramp. Conventionally a scissor ramp or jack is used for lifting a vehicle for various purposes, to lift the body to appreciable height, and many other applications also such ramps can be used for various purposes like maintenance and many material handling operations. It can be of mechanical, pneumatic or hydraulic type. The design described in this is developed keeping in mind that the ramp can be operated by mechanical means by using wire ropes with the help of electric motor.
3. **Muzaffar Othman Abdulla, [3]** In this research paper Mr. Muzaffar has dealt with concept of Design and development a multi-portable lift platform trolleys for the warehouses and markets. The knowledge application obtained from Master's University study and practical experience in various companies has been the main and most important objective of this study and is also the fundamental task solution for the creation and design of hydraulic multi-portable lift trolleys which has double platform lift scissors.
4. **Er. G.S. Ramteke, et.al [4]** This paper is about analysis of wire rope. The paper presents a study carried out on simple 7 wire single strand rope using the analytical approach. The results obtained are compared. It is concluded that the behaviour is significantly altered when rotation of the wire rope is allowed and when the rotation is prevented. Each case has been analyzed and presented.
5. **S.D. Wankhede, et.al [5]** In this is paper, they have developed a mechanism of hydraulic scissor lift. This paper deals with analysis and optimization of hydraulic scissor lift. CATIA is used for modelling purpose. The main aim is to reduce lift weight by modifying parameters like the cylinder position and replacing supporting link of cylinder ultimately reducing the cost.
6. **Suraj B. Dhanawade, et.al [6]** In this paper resolves problem of material handling for cold storage industry. Goods were in cartoons which are likely to be perished if not loaded to cold room in stipulated time. The aim of this paper is design, analysis and to fabricate a hydraulic scissor lift which lifts maximum 2000 kg load with minimum time. Lifting height achieved by scissor mechanism is of 2 m from bottom level. The aim of this paper is design, analysis and to fabricate a hydraulic scissor lift which operates efficiently and consistently and it should be compact and cost effective. Deformation analysis, beam 188 reaction forces, equivalent stress analysis of

scissor were done by ANSYS design software and buckling and bending failure analysis were also done in this paper.

7. **Mr. Dayal Singh Rathore, et.al [7]** The following paper describes the design as well as analysis of a hydraulic scissor lift. Conventionally a scissor lift or jack is used for lifting a vehicle to change a tire, to gain access to go to the underside of the vehicle, to lift the body to appreciable height, and many other applications also such lifts can be used for various purposes like maintenance and many material handling operations. It can be of mechanical, pneumatic or hydraulic type. The design described in the paper is developed keeping in mind that the lift can be operated by mechanical means by using pantograph so that the overall cost of the scissor lift is reduced.
8. **Cengiz Görkem Dengiz, et.al [8]** In These systems are mainly preferred to do maintenance, repair, and clean. In this study, the design and analysis of a scissor lift system were performed with having a load carrying capacity of 500kg and a working height of 2m. The solid model and assembly of the system have been developed by the Solid Works program. The structural analysis of the system was also investigated with the help of the same program i.e. stress, deflection, and safety factor values of system elements were obtained.
9. **Bekir Cirak, [9]** In this study, model of lifting platform consisting of scissors and hydraulic cylinder is formed. Static state equations have been used for the mathematical model of the mechanism. The weights and mass inertia moments of the platform members and the upper table have been neglected. Vehicle load as a point force, the top of the table is closed at the moment when the mechanism is effective.
10. **Sabde Abhijit Manoharrao, et.al [10]** The following paper describes about a hydraulic pallet lift is a mechanical device used for various applications for lifting of the loads to a height or level. A lift table is defined as a scissor lift used to stack, raise or lower, convey and/or transfer material between two or more elevations. The main objective of the devices used for lifting purposes is to make the table adjustable to a desired height.

III. Methodology

3.1 Methodology Flow Chart

Fig 2 Methodology flow chart

1. Project requirement is the general conditions and objectives that to be implemented for completion of the project. It is only done by proper planning.
2. Collection of relevant data which is related to the project from review of journals, reference book, publish paper, etc. There are various sources from which design calculation related data or relevant theory are available. It is important that field visit to be done at least once that place those related to project and relevant information to be noted.

3. Material selection play main role in project design. The selecting of proper material for respective machine parts depends on the purpose and type of operation. Design modeling and analysis is also important parameters to achieve desired objectives of the project.
4. Optimization is a method of obtaining best result under the given essential conditions. It plays a vital role in machine design because the mechanical components are to be designed in an optimal manner. Design of components of the mechanical lift includes finding of each member of the lift by considering the force acting on the member and the permissible stresses for the material used. FEM is used to analysis of stress, it shows the particular failure of member in design then it is necessary to modification of particular design due to which it would not fail again. Then fabrication is to be done as per final modification detailed drawing. Then final method is the experiment and testing, in that the load is to be check whether the model is either safe or not.

3.2 Design of Machine Element

Design of machine elements is the most important step in the complete procedure of machine design. In order to ensure the basic requirements of machine elements, calculations are carried out to find out the dimensions of the machine elements. These calculations form an integral part of the design of machine elements. It consists of the following steps :

1. Specification of Function
2. Determination of Forces
3. Failure Criterion
4. Determination of Dimensions

Fig 3 Structural diagram of loading and unloading platform

3.3 Material Selection

- **Mild Steel**

Low carbon steel contains less than 0.3 % carbon. It is popular as ‘mild steel’. Low carbon steels are soft and very ductile. They can be easily machined and easily welded. However, due to low carbon content, they are unresponsive to heat treatment. Low carbon steels can be satisfactorily welded. However, low carbon steels are the most easily welded. Higher the percentage of carbon in steel, more difficult it is to weld. Therefore, welded assemblies re made of low carbon steels.

▪ High Carbon Steel

High carbon steel contains more than 0.5 % carbon. They are called hard steels or tool steels. High carbon steels respond readily to heat treatments. When heat treated, high carbon steels have very high strength combined with hardness. They do not have much ductility as compared with low and medium carbon steels. High carbon steels are difficult to weld. Excessive hardness is often accompanied by excessive brittleness. Plain carbon steels are available in the form of bar, tube, plate, sheet and wire.

▪ Stainless Steel

The chromium steels containing 12 to 14 percent chromium and 0.12 to 0.35 percent carbon are the first stainless steels developed. Since these steels possess martensitic structure, therefore, they are called martensitic stainless steels. These steels are magnetic and may be hardened by suitable heat treatment and the hardness obtainable depends upon the carbon content. These steels can be easily welded and machined. When formability, softness, etc. are required in fabrication, steel having 0.12 percent maximum carbon is often used in soft condition. With increasing carbon, it is possible by hardening and tempering to obtain tensile strength in the range of 600 to 900 N/mm². Weld delay does not occurs due to spot welding.

▪ Alloy Steel

Alloy steel is defined as carbon steel to which one or more alloying elements are added to obtain certain beneficial effects. The commonly added elements include silicon, manganese, nickel, chromium, molybdenum and tungsten. The term 'alloy steels' usually refers to 'low' alloy steels containing from about 1 to 4 percent of alloying elements. Plain carbon steels are successfully used for components subjected to low or medium stresses. Alloying elements have different effects on the properties of metals such as it increases strength and hardness, improve stability in different temperatures, increases oxidation resistance, enhancement of hardenability, improvement of creep and fatigue resistance, etc.

3.4 Components

Components used in this project are as follows :

1. Platform
2. Ramp

3. Platform Guardrail
4. Column
5. Base
6. Supporter
7. Motor Stand
8. Wire Rope
9. Wire Rope Drum
10. Wire Rope Sheave
11. Gear Motor
12. Shaft
13. Special Slider
14. Pillow Block Bearing
15. Bulldog Grip
16. Hinge
17. Link Chain
18. Fixed Support Leg
19. Wheel Chock
20. LT Control Switch
21. Polyurethane Wheel

3.5 Assumption of the design

The design of mechanical lift is to lift up to 2.8 m and carrying load capacity of 877.5 kg including factor of safety is 1.5 at a velocity of 0.25 m/s, which is driven by gear motor of 4 KW and gear ratio is 10:1. The structure of the lift will build with mild steel because its strength, stiffness and availability in market. The lifting will be at two heights of 1.2 m and 2.8 m because of two compartments were found to the bike carrier truck while visited at showroom. Column height will be 3.6 m. The lifting platform sheet dimension is a length of 2.6 m, width of 2.4 m and thickness of 0.005 m. The connected ramp size having length of 2.7 m, width of 0.5 m and thickness of 0.005 m. The overall dimensions of the mechanical lift having length of 4.154 m, width of 3.37 m and height of 3.6 m.

IV. Design Calculations

4.1 Design Calculations

For 3 bullet bike or any 4 bike (including MCWG /MCWOG) which weight equal to bullet weight.

For 3 bullet bike

$195 \times 3 = 585 \text{ kg}$

Load to be lifted = $585 \times 1.5 = 877.5 \text{ kg}$ (considering FOS)

Height to be lifted

First height – 1200 mm

Final height – 2800 mm

Design of each component of the mechanical lift are as follows:

4.1.1 Platform

Quantity : 01

Material : Mild Steel

Platform basement

Component details

Shape/Section : Hollow square

Length : 0.05 m

Width : 0.05 m

Thickness : 0.003 m

Area of hollow square = $(0.05 \times 0.05) - (0.044 \times 0.044) = 5.64 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$

Structural details

Shape/Section : Rectangular frame with hollow square pipes

Length : 2.7 m

Width : 2.4 m

Actual Volume = Volume of structure – Material reduction

Volume of structure = $[5.64 \times 10^{-4} (2.7 + 2.7 + 2.4 + 2.4)] + (9 \times 2.6 \times 5.64 \times 10^{-4}) = 0.0189504 \text{ m}^3$

Note : Material reduction will done while cutting of hollow pipes for the fitting properly.

Material reduction for 4 sides (V_{cut}) = $\{[(2 \times \frac{1}{2} \times 0.05 \times 0.05 \times 0.003) + (0.05 \times 0.044 \times 0.003)]2\}4 = 1.128 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3$

Actual Volume = $0.0189504 - 1.128 \times 10^{-4} = 0.0188376 \text{ m}^3$

Platform Sheet

Shape/Section : Solid rectangular

Length : 2.6 m

Width : 2.4 m

Thickness : 0.005 m

Volume = $2.6 \times 2.4 \times 0.005 = 0.0312 \text{ m}^3$

Volume of platform = $0.0188376 + 0.0312 = 0.0500376 \text{ m}^3$

Mass of platform = Density x Volume = 7860×0.0500376

Mass of platform = 393.295536 kg

Weight = 3858.229208 N = 3.858229208 KN

4.1.2 Ramp

Quantity : 02

Material : Mild Steel

Shape/Section : Solid rectangular

Length : 2.7 m

Width : 0.5 m

Thickness : 0.005 m

Mass of ramp = Density x Volume = $2 \times 7860 \times 2.7 \times 0.5 \times 0.005$

Mass of ramp = 106.11 kg

Weight = 1040.9391 N = 1.0409391 KN

4.1.3 Platform Guardrail

Quantity : 02

Material : Mild Steel

Component details

Shape/Section : Hollow square

Length : 0.05 m

Width : 0.05 m

Thickness : 0.003 m

Area of the hollow square = $(0.05 \times 0.05) - (0.044 \times 0.044) = 5.64 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$ Structural details

Shape/Section : Rectangular frame with hollow square pipes

Length : 2.4 m

Width : 0.7 m

Actual Volume = Volume of structure – Material reduction

Volume of structure = $[5.64 \times 10^{-4} (2.4 + 2.4 + 0.7 + 0.7)] + [5.64 \times 10^{-4} (1.07 + 0.6 + 1.49)] = 5.27904 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$

Note : Material reduction will done while cutting of hollow pipes for the fitting properly.

Material reduction for 4 sides (V_{cut}) = $\{[(2 \times \frac{1}{2} \times 0.05 \times 0.05 \times 0.003) + (0.05 \times 0.044 \times 0.003)] \times 4\} = 1.128 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3$ Actual Volume = $5.27904 \times 10^{-3} - 1.128 \times 10^{-4} = 5.16624 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$ Mass of guardrail = Density x Volume = $2 \times 7860 \times 5.16624 \times 10^{-3}$ **Mass of platform guardrail = 81.2132928 kg****Weight = 796.7024024 N = 0.7967024024 KN****4.1.4 Column**

Quantity : 02

Material : Mild Steel

Component details

Shape/Section : I section

Length : 0.125 m

Width : 0.1 m

Thickness : 0.008 m

Area of I section = $(0.125 \times 0.1) - \{(0.125 - 0.016) \times (0.1 - 0.008)\} = 2.472 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$

Structural details

Shape/Section : Solid I section

Length : 3.6 m

Volume of I section = $2.472 \times 10^{-3} \times 3.6 = 8.8992 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$ Mass of column = Density x Volume = $2 \times 7860 \times 8.8992 \times 10^{-3}$ **Mass of column = 139.895424 kg****Weight = 1372.374109 N = 1.372374109 KN****4.1.5 Base**

Quantity : 01

Material : Mild Steel

Component details

Shape/Section : Hollow Rectangular

Length : 0.15 m

Width : 0.1 m

Thickness : 0.01 m

Area of hollow rectangular = $(0.15 \times 0.1) - (0.13 \times 0.08) = 4.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$ Structural details

Shape/Section : C section frame with hollow rectangular pipes

Length : 2.98 m

Width : 2.55 m

Actual Volume = Volume of structure – Material reduction

Volume of structure = $4.6 \times 10^{-3} (2.98 + 2.55 + 2.55) = 0.037168 \text{ m}^3$

Note : Material reduction will done while cutting of hollow pipes for the fitting properly.

Material reduction for 2 sides (V_{cut}) = $\{[(2 \times \frac{1}{2} \times 0.1 \times 0.1 \times 0.01) + (0.15 \times 0.13 \times 0.01)] \times 2\} = 1.18 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$ Actual Volume = $0.037168 - 1.18 \times 10^{-3} = 0.035988 \text{ m}^3$ Mass of base = Density x Volume = 7860×0.035988 **Mass of base = 282.86568 kg****Weight = 2774.912321 N = 2.774912321 KN**

4.1.6 Supporter

Quantity : 01

Material : Mild Steel

Component details

Shape/Section : Hollow square

Length : 0.08 m

Width : 0.08 m

Thickness : 0.005 m

Area of hollow square = $(0.08 \times 0.08) - (0.07 \times 0.07) = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$

Structural details

Shape/Section : Rectangular frame with hollow square pipes

Length : 2.98 m

Width : 1.5275 m

Height : 1 m

Actual Volume = Volume of structure – Material reduction

Volume of structure = $1.5 \times 10^{-3} [1.5275 + 1.5275 + 2.98 + (1.5275 - 0.08) + (1.5275 - 0.08) + (2.98 - 0.16) + (1 - 0.08) + (1 - 0.08)] = 0.020385 \text{ m}^3$

Note : Material reduction will done while cutting of hollow pipes for the fitting properly.

Material reduction for 2 sides (V_{cut}) = $\{[(2 \times \frac{1}{2} \times 0.08 \times 0.08 \times 0.005) + (0.08 \times 0.07 \times 0.005)]2\}2 = 2.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3$

Actual Volume = $0.020385 - 2.4 \times 10^{-4} = 0.020145 \text{ m}^3$

Mass of supporter = Density x Volume = 7860×0.020145

Mass of supporter = 158.3397 kg

Weight = 1553.312457 N = 1.553312457 KN

4.1.7 Motor Stand

Quantity : 01

Material : Mild Steel

Component details

Shape/Section : Hollow square

Length : 0.08 m

Width : 0.08 m

Thickness : 0.005 m

Area of hollow square = $(0.08 \times 0.08) - (0.07 \times 0.07) = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$

Structural details

Shape/Section : Rectangular frame with hollow square pipes

Length : 4.154 m

Width : 0.9 m

Actual Volume = Volume of structure – Material reduction

Volume of structure = $[1.5 \times 10^{-3} (4.154 + 0.9 + 0.9 + 1.174)] + [4.6 \times 10^{-3} (0.82 + 0.82 + 0.82)] = 0.022008 \text{ m}^3$

Note : Material reduction will done while cutting of hollow pipes for the fitting properly.

Material reduction for 4 sides (V_{cut}) = $\{[(2 \times \frac{1}{2} \times 0.08 \times 0.08 \times 0.005) + (0.08 \times 0.07 \times 0.005)]2\}4 = 4.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3$

Actual Volume = $0.022008 - 4.8 \times 10^{-4} = 0.021528 \text{ m}^3$

Mass of motor stand = Density x Volume = 7860×0.021528

Mass of motor stand = 169.21008 kg

Weight = 1659.950885 N = 1.659950885 KN

4.1.8 Wire Rope

Design a wire rope for loading and unloading platform machine. The operation is conducted in two level having initial and final height are 1.2 m and 2.8 m respectively. Three bullet is lifted on platform having weight of 195 kg each at velocity of 0.25 m/s. Time required to reach at initial and final height are 4.8 s and 11.2 s respectively. The weight of platform structure is 588 kg. Factor of safety is 1.5.

Given data :

Initial height, $H_1 = 1.2 \text{ m}$

Final height, $H_2 = 2.8 \text{ m}$

Number of bullet bike = 3

Weight of bullet bike = 195 kg

Velocity, $v = 0.25 \text{ m/s}$

Initial time, $T_1 = 4.8 \text{ s}$

Final time, $T_2 = 11.2 \text{ s}$

Weight of platform structure = 588 kg

Factor of safety = 1.5

Solution :

Load to be lifted on platform = $195 \times 3 = 585 \times 1.5 = 877.5$ kg (considering FOS)

Self weight of platform structure = 588 kg

Total weight lifted in the operation = 1466 kgf = 14381.46 N

Average lifting height $\frac{1.2 + 2.8}{2} = 2$ m

Average time required to reach at height of 2 m = $\frac{4.8 + 11.2}{2} = 8$ s

Step 1 : Selection of wire rope

Wire rope has to be designed for loading and unloading platform which comes under an elevator so we selected wire rope 6 x 19 class 3 from PSG design data book having page no. 9.1.

Step 2 : Calculation of design load

Design Load = $2.5 \times$ Load to be lifted \times Assumed factor of safety

By considering given rope application, 6 x 19 class 3 wire rope selected for further design calculation from page no 9.1 of PSG design data book.

Factor of safety = 5

Design Load = $2.5 \times 14381.46 \times 5$

Design Load = 179768.25 N

Step 3 : Selection of wire rope diameter (d)

Assuming the design load as breaking load, selected the wire rope diameter from PSG design data book page no. 9.5.

Design Load = 179768.25 N

Design Load = 18.325 Tonnes

Diameter of wire rope (d) = 18 mm

Step 4 : Calculation of drum diameter (D)

By using the selected type of wire rope, ratio of drum diameter to rope diameter selected from PSG design data book page no. 9.1. Drum diameter is calculated from this ratio.

For the selected wire rope 6 x 19 class 3.

$$\frac{D}{d} = 23$$

$$\frac{D}{18} = 23$$

Drum diameter (D) = 414 mm

Step 5 : Selection of useful cross sectional area (A)

Using the formula of 'A' given in PSG design data book page no. 9.1, area of useful cross section of the wire rope is calculated.

$$A = 0.4 \times \frac{\pi}{4} d^2$$

$$A = 0.4 \times \frac{\pi}{4} 18^2$$

Useful cross sectional area (A) = 101.79 mm²

Step 6 : Calculation of wire diameter (d_w)

$$d_w = \frac{d}{1.5 \times \sqrt{i}}$$

Where, i = Number of strands x number of wires in each strand

$$d_w = \frac{18}{1.5 \times \sqrt{6 \times 19}}$$

Wire diameter (d_w) = 1.124 mm

Step 7 : Selection of weight of wire rope (W_r)

For the selected diameter of wire rope from PSG design data book page no. 9.5, weight of wire rope is selected from

$$W_r = 1.25 \text{ kgf/m}$$

$$W_r = 12.26 \text{ N/m}$$

For 20 m length,

$$W_r = 12.26 \times 20$$

$$\text{Weight of wire rope } (W_r) = 245.2 \text{ N}$$

Step 8 : Calculation of effective load (W_{ea})

$$W_{ea} = W_d + W_b + W_a$$

Where,

W_{ea} = Effective Load

W_d = Direct Load

W_b = Bending Load

W_a = Acceleration Load

$$W_d = W + W_r$$

$$W_b = E' \frac{d_w}{D} A$$

$$W_a = \left(\frac{W + W_r}{g} \right) a$$

$$a = \left(\frac{v_2 + v_1}{t} \right)$$

Where,

W = Weight to be lifted

W_r = Weight of wire rope

E' = Corrected modulus of elasticity

v_1 = Initial velocity

$$W_d = 14381.46 + 245.2 = 14626.66 \text{ N}$$

$$E' = 0.8 \times 106 \text{ kgf/cm}^2 = 78480 \text{ N/mm}^2 \text{ (given in PSG design data book page no. 9.1)}$$

$$W_b = 78480 \times \frac{1.124}{414} \times 101.79 = 21688.53 \text{ N}$$

$$W_a = \left(\frac{14381.46 + 245.5}{9.81} \right) \left(\frac{0.25 + 0}{8} \right) = 46.60 \text{ N}$$

$$W_{ea} = 14626.66 + 21688.53 + 46.60$$

Effective load (W_{ea}) = 36361.79 N

Step 9 : Calculation of factor of safety

Working factor of safety = $\frac{\text{Breaking load of selected wire rope}}{\text{Effective load}}$

$$\text{Working factor of safety} = \frac{179768.25}{36361.79}$$

Working factor of safety = 4.944

Note : The working factor of safety is not greater than the recommended factor of safety hence the design is not safe. So number of wire rope must be calculated.

Step 10 : Calculation of number of wire ropes

Number of wire ropes = $\frac{\text{Recommended factor of safety}}{\text{Working factor of safety}}$

$$\text{Number of wire ropes} = \frac{5}{4.944}$$

Number of wire rope = 1

Step 11 : Calculation of tensile strength of wire rope (σ_u)

By using the formula of 'P' from PSG design data book page no. 9.1, tensile strength is calculated.

$$P = \frac{F\sigma_u}{\frac{\sigma_u}{n} - \left(\frac{d}{D} \times \frac{d_w}{d} \times E'\right)}$$

Where,

P = Breaking strength of wire rope (N)

F = Load or tension per fall of wire rope (N)

D = Diameter of drum (mm)

d = Diameter of wire rope (mm)

d_w = Diameter of wire (mm)

σ_u = Tensile strength of wire rope (N/mm²)

n = Stress factor or design factor = n' x duty factor

E' = Corrected modulus of elasticity of steel wire rope (N/mm²)

$n = 5 \times 1.4 = 7$

Here, design load is taken as breaking strength of wire rope

Table 1 Number of fall system

Number of fall system	Tonnes
4	< 25
8	25 – 75
12	> 75

Selected number of fall system according to value of tonnes.

$$F = \frac{W}{\text{number of fall} \times \text{efficiency}}$$

Assuming efficiency = 90%

$$F = \frac{14381.46}{4 \times 0.9} = 3995\text{N}$$

$$179768.25 = \frac{3995 \times \sigma_u}{\frac{\sigma_u}{7} - \left(\frac{18}{414} \times \frac{1.124}{18} \times 78480 \right)}$$

Tensile strength of wire rope (σ_u) = 1767 N/mm²

1767 N/mm² = 180 kgf/mm² (175-190 kgf/mm² as per PSG design data book page no. 9.1.)

Step 12 : Calculation of fatigue load of wire rope (p)

$$p = \frac{2F}{dD}$$

$$p = \frac{2 \times 3995}{18 \times 414}$$

Fatigue load (p) = 1.07 N/mm²

Step 13 : Selection of duty factor and life of mechanism

We selected the duty factor and life of mechanism for mechanism class 3 from PSG design data book page no. 9.2.

Table 2 Duty factor and life of mechanism

Mechanism class	Duty factor		Average life		
	Strength	Wear	Running (hrs/day)	Total life (hrs)	Days per year on 20 years life
3	1.4	0.6	3	Over 26000	333

The design factor is obtained by multiplying the factor of safety for the appropriate class by the duty factor.

Step 14 : Life of wire rope

Equation for life of rope is taken from PSG design data book page no. 9.7 is given by

$$N = \frac{0.4 Z}{a\beta Z_2}$$

Where,

N = rope life in month of 25 days

Z = number of repeated bends corresponding to m

a, β & Z₂ = constant values given in PSG design data book page no. 9.8.

$$\frac{D}{d} = (m \cdot \sigma \cdot C_1 \cdot C_2 \cdot C) + 8$$

Where,

$$\text{Tensile stress in wire rope } (\sigma) = \frac{10F}{\pi d^2} = \frac{10 \times 3995}{\pi (18)^2} = 39.45 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

values of C₁ and C taken from table 3 and 4 of PSG design data book page no. 9.8 respectively.

C₂ = 0.63 to 1.15 depending on the rope material and its treatment.

$$23 = (m \times 39.45 \times 1 \times 0.9 \times 0.95) + 8$$

$$m = 0.45 = 45$$

Z is calculated by interpolation by using table 1 in PSG design data book page no. 9.8.

$$\frac{50000 - 70000}{50000 - Z} = \frac{0.41 - 0.56}{0.41 - 0.45}$$

$$Z = 55333$$

$$N = \frac{0.4 Z}{a\beta Z_2} = \frac{0.4 \times 55333}{1000 \times 0.5 \times 4} = 11$$

Life of wire rope (N) = 11 months

4.1.9 Wire Rope Drum

Step 1 : Calculation of drum dimensions

Drum dimensions can be calculated by using PSG design data book page no. 9.2 and 9.3.

Number of turns on the drum for one rope

$$Z = \frac{H_i}{\pi D} + 2$$

Where,

H = height to which load is raised (mm)

Z = number of turns on the drum for one rope member

i = ratio of the pulley system

i is the mechanical advantages in this system so,

$$i = \frac{\text{Number of falls}}{2} = \frac{4}{2} = 2$$

$$Z = \frac{2800 \times 2}{\pi \times 414} + 2$$

Number of turns (Z) = 7

Length of the drum for one wire rope system

$$L = \left(\frac{2H_i}{\pi D} + 7 \right) \times S$$

Where,

L = Length of drum (mm)

S = pitch of the grooves on the drum (mm)

Selected standard groove for wire rope having diameter 18 mm from table of PSG design data book page no. 9.9.

Selected $d = 19.5$ mm, we get $r_1 = 11.5$ mm, $S_1 = 22$ mm & $C_1 = 5$ mm

Now,

$$L = \left(\frac{2 \times 2800 \times 2}{\pi \times 414} + 7 \right) \times 22$$

Length of drum (L) = 344 mm

Dimensions of wire rope drum using empirical relations :

Depth of grooves = $0.1 d = 0.1 \times 18 = 1.8$ mm

Wall thickness of drum (w) = $0.02 D + (0.6 \text{ to } 1.0) = 0.02 \times 414 + (6.72) = 15$ mm

Inner diameter of drum (D_i) = $D - 2w = 414 - 2(15) = 384$ mm

Diameter of flange (D_f) = $D + 6d = 414 + 6(18) = 522$ mm

Step 2 : Calculation of weight of wire rope drum

Quantity : 02

Material : Mild Steel

Flange

Quantity : 02

Shape/Section : Solid circular

Diameter : 0.522 m

Thickness : 0.015 m

$$\text{Volume of flange} = 2 \times \frac{\pi}{4} \times (0.522)^2 \times 0.015 = 6.42 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$$

Drum

Component details

Shape/Section : Hollow circular

Outer diameter : 0.414 m

Wall thickness : 0.015 m

$$\text{Area of hollow circular portion} = \frac{\pi}{4} [(0.414)^2 - (0.384)^2] = 0.0188 \text{ m}^2$$

Structural details

Shape/Section : Hollow circular pipe

Length : 0.314 m

$$\text{Volume of drum} = 0.0188 \times 0.314 = 5.90 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$$

$$\text{Volume of wire rope drum} = 6.42 \times 10^{-3} + 5.90 \times 10^{-3} = 0.01232 \text{ m}^3$$

$$\text{Mass of wire rope drum} = \text{Density} \times \text{Volume} = 2 \times 7860 \times 0.01232$$

$$\text{Mass of wire rope drum} = \mathbf{193.6704 \text{ kg}}$$

$$\text{Weight} = \mathbf{1900 \text{ N} = 1.9 \text{ KN}}$$

4.1.10 Wire Rope Sheave

Step 1 : Design of sheave

Sheave, sheave axle and sheave axle bearing is to be design in this step.

There are total 4 sheaves are used. The sheaves are joined in such a manner that axes of upper sheaves are perpendicular to the axes of lower sheaves. Total load is lifted by wire rope is 14381.46 N with the help of 2 upper sheaves. Remaining two lower sheaves are act as a supporting sheave which helps to transmitted the load in perpendicular direction towards the rope drum. Hence, we considered the load carried member is two upper sheaves so, each sheave carried a load of 7190.73 N. We neglected minor load acted on two lower sheaves.

Assumed transmission efficiency is 90% in between wire rope and sheaves.

$$F = \frac{W}{0.9} = \frac{7190.73}{0.9} = 7990 \text{ N}$$

Selection of sheave

Selected the standard sheave for wire rope diameter of 18 mm from PSG design data book page no. 9.10.

Selecting, $d = 19.5 \text{ mm}$,

$a = 55 \text{ mm}$, $b = 40 \text{ mm}$, $c = 10 \text{ mm}$, $e = 1.5 \text{ mm}$, $h = 30 \text{ mm}$, $l = 15 \text{ mm}$, $r = 12 \text{ mm}$, $r_1 = 5 \text{ mm}$, $r_2 = 5 \text{ mm}$, $r_3 = 17 \text{ mm}$ & $r_4 = 10 \text{ mm}$.

Length of sheave hub (l_h) = 20 % more of a $l_h = 1.2 a = 1.2 \times 55 = 66 \text{ mm}$

$$\text{PCD of rope sheave} = \text{Nominal tread diameter} + 2 \left(\frac{\text{wire rope diameter}}{2} \right)$$

$$\text{Pitch Circle Diameter of rope sheave} = 120 + 2(18/2) = 138 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{PCD} = 138 \text{ mm}$$

Design of sheave axle

Fig 4 Sheave axle carrying wire rope sheave

We selected 45C8 as material of sheave axle. As per IS 1570, IS 2004, IS 2507 & PSG design data book page no. 1.9, the chemical compositions and mechanical properties of carbon steel are as follows :

Table 3 Chemical composition of carbon steel (45C8)

Carbon (%)	Manganese (%)	Phosphorus (%)	Silicon (%)	Sulphur (%)
0.40 – 0.50	0.60 - 0.90	0.04	0.15 – 0.35	0.04

Table 4 Mechanical properties of carbon steel (45C8)

Properties	Umit	Metric Value
Ultimate tensile strength (σ_{ut})	MPa	670
Yield tensile strength (σ_{yt})	MPa	480
Young's modulus (E)	GPa	200
Bulk modulus (K)	GPa	140
Shear modulus (G)	GPa	80
Elongation	%	15
Poissons ratio	-	0.3
Reduction of area	%	40
Izod impact	Nm	41
Brinell hardness (HB)	-	163
Rockwell hardness (HR)	-	84
Vickers hardness (HV)	-	170

Assumed factor of safety is 3 for repeated loading.

$$\sigma_t = \sigma_b = \frac{\sigma_{yt}}{3} = \frac{480}{3} = 160 \text{ MPa}$$

Considering vertical load diagram, $R_A + R_C = 7990 \text{ N}$

To find, taking moment about point A, $\sum M_A = 0$

$$7990 \times 62.5 - R_C \times 125 = 0$$

$$R_C = 3995 \text{ N} \ \& \ R_A = 3995 \text{ N}$$

Bending moment at point B, $M_B = 3995 \times 62.5 = 249687.5 \text{ Nmm}$

Axle is subjected to bending moment only. Therefore, the axle can be designed by using the equation,

$$M = \frac{\pi}{32} \times \sigma_b \times (d_a)^3$$

$$249687.5 = \frac{\pi}{32} \times 160 \times (d_a)^3$$

Diameter of sheave axle (d_a) = 26 mm

Selection of bearing between sheave axle and rope sheave

The radial load acting on the bearing

$$F_r = 2F = 2 \times 3995 = 7990 \text{ N} = 7.99 \text{ KN} = 8 \text{ KN}$$

F_r is equal to 8 KN which is high and there is possibility of axle to tilt so, spherical roller bearing is selected.

Selected condition of hoisting is light duty and considered 8 hrs/day from PSG design data book page no. 9.8.

Assumed life of bearing is 2 year, $L_h = 2 \times 12 \times 25 \times 8 = 4800 \text{ hrs}$

Life in millions of revolutions :

$$L_{mr} = \frac{L_h \times N \times 60}{10^6}$$

Where,

N = speed of wire rope sheave (rpm)

$$V = \frac{\pi DN}{60}$$

Where,

V = speed of pulley or rope sheave (m/s)

D = PCD of rope sheave or pulley (m)

This formula is used to find speed of rope sheave

$$\text{Speed of pulley (V)} = \text{hoist speed} \times \frac{\text{number of fall}}{2} = 0.25 \times \frac{4}{2} = 0.5 \text{ m/s}$$

$$N = \frac{V \times 60}{\pi D} = \frac{0.5 \times 60}{\pi \times 0.138} = 69 \text{ rpm}$$

$$L_{mr} = \frac{L_h \times N \times 60}{10^6} = \frac{4800 \times 69 \times 60}{10^6} = 19.872 \text{ mr}$$

Assumed 90 % probability of survival

Life of bearing for 90 % survival at 19.872 mr,

$$L_{60} = 19.872 \text{ mr}$$

From PSG design data book page no. 4.2. Equivalent load (P_E) is given by

$$P_E = (X V F_r + Y F_a) S K_t$$

Where,

X = radial factor

V = race rotation factor

F_r = radial load (N)

Y = thrust factor

F_a = axial load (N)

S = service factor

K_t = temperature factor

$$P_E = (1 \times 1.2 \times 7990 + 0) 1.3 \times 1 = 12464.4 \text{ N}$$

From PSG design data book page no. 4.2. Dynamic capacity (C) is given by

$$C = \left(\frac{L}{L_{10}} \right)^{\frac{1}{K}} \times P_E = \left(\frac{L_{60}}{L_{10}} \right)^{\frac{1}{K}} \times P_E$$

$$C = \left(\frac{19.872}{1} \right)^{\frac{3}{10}} \times 12464.4$$

$$C = 30559 \text{ N}$$

Where,

L = required life of bearing in million of revolutions (mr) [$L_{60} = 19.872$ mr]

L_{10} = life of the bearing for 90 % survival at 1 mr (mr) [$L_{10} = 1$ mr]

$$K = \frac{10}{3} \text{ for roller bearing}$$

Selected a standard spherical roller bearing for $C = 30559$ $N = 3115$ kgf

As per spherical roller bearing table from PSG design data book page no. 4.32, having bearing series 222 C.

Table 5 Spherical roller bearing data sheet

Specification	Unit	Values
Bearing number	-	22206 C
Bore diameter (d)	Mm	30
Outer diameter (D)	Mm	62
Nominal width (B)	Mm	20
Edge reduction (r)	Mm	1.5
Inner distance between two rollers (E)	Mm	38
Static capacity (C_0)	KN	31
Dynamic capacity (C)	KN	45
Maximum permissible speed	rpm	6000

The bore diameter of bearing is greater than diameter of sheave axle. But the bearing is fixed within the bore of sheave. Hence we considered the bore diameter of this bearing as a sheave axle diameter. This bearing is lies between rope sheave and sheave axel which allows the rotate outer race.

Diameter of sheave axle (d_a) = 30 mm

Step 2 : Calculation of weight of wire rope sheave

Where,

ΦD_1 = Outside diameter

ΦD_2 = Nominal tread diameter

ΦH = Hub diameter

ΦB = Hub bore diameter

ΦG = Bearing bore diameter

E = Rim width

F = Hub width

R = Groove radius

Fig 5 Blueprint of wire rope sheave

Quantity : 04

Material : Ductile Cast Iron (GGG 60)

Bearing used : Spherical roller bearing

Sheave axle

Quantity : 01

Material : Carbon Steel (45C8)

Shape/Section : Solid circular

Diameter : 0.03 m

Length : 0.125 m

Mass of sheave axle = Volume \times Density = $\frac{\pi}{4}(0.03)^2 \times 0.125 \times 7850 = 0.69$ kg

Cover plate

Cover plate is to be cut in such a way that the sheave axle is inserted within it on both side before weld joint to it.

Quantity : 02

Material : Mild Steel

Shape/Section : Solid rectangular

Length : 0.18 m

Width : 0.1 m

Thickness : 0.008 m

Actual Volume = Volume of structure – Material reduction

Actual Volume = $(0.18 \times 0.1 \times 0.008) - \frac{\pi}{4}(0.03)^2 \times 0.008 = 1.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{m}^3$

Mass of cover plate = 2 x Density x Volume = $2 \times 7860 \times 1.4 \times 10^{-4} = 2.2$ kg

Base plate

Quantity : 01

Material : Mild Steel

Shape/Section : Solid rectangular

Length : 0.125 m

Width : 0.1 m

Thickness : 0.01 m

Mass of base plate = $0.125 \times 0.1 \times 0.01 \times 7860 = 0.9825$ kg

Four sheaves are used in this lifting machine

Mass of wire rope sheave = 4(mass of sheave + mass of sheave axle + mass of cover plate + mass of base plate) + extra material requirement at lower sides

Mass of wire rope sheave = $4(8+0.69+2.2+0.9825) + 5$

Mass of wire rope sheave = 52.49 kg

Weight = 514.9269 N = 0.5149269 KN

Table 6 Specification chart of wire rope sheave

Sl. No.	Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values
1.	Rope diameter	D	mm	18
2.	Bearing number	-	-	22206 C
3.	Outside diameter	ΦD_1	mm	180
4.	Nominal tread diameter	ΦD_2	mm	120
5.	Hub diameter	ΦH	mm	88
6.	Hub bore diameter	ΦB	mm	62
7.	Bearing bore diameter	ΦG	mm	30
8.	Rim width	E	mm	55
9.	Hub width	F	mm	66
10.	Groove radius	R	mm	9.5
11.	Mass	M	kg	8

4.1.11 Gear Motor

Selection of gear motor

Calculation for required input power for motor

Relation between work and power

$$W = F \times D$$

$$W = 14381.46 \times 2$$

$$W = 28762.92 \text{ Nm}$$

Where,

W = Work done (J or Nm)

F = Load applied (N)

D = Distance to be travelled (m)

Initial requirement for selecting motor is given as follows :

The machine is operated at two level of heights, so we have taken average height 2 m for ease of calculation.

There is 8 sec required to reach the average height of 2 m.

$$P_{out} = \frac{W}{t} = \frac{28762.92}{8} = 3595.365 \text{ Watt}$$

Output power (P_{out}) = 3595.365 W

Assumed, efficiency of motor (η) = 90%

$$\eta = \frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}}$$

$$P_{in} = \frac{P_{out}}{\eta} = \frac{3595.365}{0.9} = 3994.85 \text{ Watt}$$

Input power (P_{in}) = 3994.85 W

Note: As we have used gear motor, efficiency is the ratio of mechanical power or gearbox power to motor power. We considered motor power approximately 4000 Watt for proper motor selection.

We have taken the reference from Chiaravalli Group SpA Gear boxes and Motors for selecting suitable motor. Selected CHM worm geared motor from Chiaravalli Group SpA book page no. 42. The motor specification of motor are as follows :

Table 7 Specification of gear motor

Type	I	N_2 (rpm)	P_1 (KW)	T_2 (Nm)	F.S.	Possible type of motor connection	
CHM 090	10	140	4	242	1.3	100/90	B5/B14

$$T_2 = \frac{9550P_1\eta}{N_2}$$

$$242 = \frac{9550 \times 4 \times \eta}{140}$$

$$\eta = 0.8869$$

Transmission efficiency (η) = 88.69 %

Where,

i = transmission ratio is called as gear ratio

N_2 = output speed (rpm)

P_1 = input power (KW)

T_2 = output torque (Nm)

Transmission ratio (i) is the ratio of motor speed to gearbox speed.

$$i = \frac{\text{Input speed}}{\text{Output speed}} = \frac{N_1}{N_2}$$

$$10 = \frac{N_1}{140}$$

Input speed (N_1) = 1400 rpm

$$\eta = \frac{\text{Output power}}{\text{Input power}} = \frac{P_2}{P_1}$$

$$0.8869 = \frac{P_2}{4}$$

Output power (P_2) = 3.5476 KW

$$P_2 = P_1 \times \eta$$

$$T_2 = \frac{9550 P_1 \eta}{N_2} = \frac{9550 P_2}{N_2}$$

This is the formula to calculate the output torque.

So, to find the input torque

$$T_1 = \frac{9550 P_1}{N_1} = \frac{9550 \times 4}{1400} = 27.29 \text{ Nm}$$

Input torque (T_1) = 27.29 Nm

Table 8 Summary of gear motor specification

Sl. No.	Parameters	Units	Values
1.	Input power (P_1)	KW	4
2.	Input speed (N_1)	rpm	1400
3.	Input torque (T_1)	Nm	27.29
4.	Output power (P_2)	KW	3.5476
5.	Output speed (N_2)	rpm	140
6.	Output torque (T_2)	Nm	242
7.	Transmission ratio (i)	-	10
8.	Transmission efficiency (η)	%	90
9.	Velocity (v)	m/s	0.25
10.	Angular velocity (ω)	rad/s	146.61

Mass of gearbox = 13 kg excluding motor as per Chiaravalli Group SpA book page no. 42.
and assumed the motor mass is 27 kg

Mass of gear motor = 40 kg

Weight = 392.4 N = 0.3924 KN

4.1.12 Shaft

Step 1 : Design of shaft

Design of shaft consisting the rope drum shaft and motor shaft are as follows:

Design of rope drum shaft

Wire rope drum is like a simply supported beam with point load at centre.

Fig 6 Rope drum and its vertical load diagram

Selected 45C8 as a material of drum shaft and we taken the value of respective stress from step 17.

$$\sigma_t = \sigma_b = 160 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\tau = \frac{160}{2} = 80 \text{ MPa}$$

Assumed length of shaft (l) = $344 + 140 + 140 = 624$ mm

Considering vertical load diagram, $R_A + R_B = 7990$ N

$$\sum M_A = 0$$

$$7990 \times 312 - R_B \times 624 = 0$$

$$R_B = 3995 \text{ N} \ \& \ R_A = 3995 \text{ N}$$

Bending moment at point B

$$M = M_C = 3995 \times 312 = 1246440 \text{ N-mm and}$$

$$M_t = T = 1725840 \text{ Nmm (taken from step 15)}$$

As per ASME code : $k_m = k_b = 1.5$ and $k_t = 1.0$ for rotating shaft (gradually applied or steady load).

As the shaft is subjected to combined twisting and bending moment

According to maximum shear stress theory

$$T_e = \sqrt{(k_m \times M)^2 + (k_t \times T)^2} = \frac{\pi}{16} \times \tau \times d^3$$

$$\sqrt{(1.5 \times 1246440)^2 + (1.0 \times 1725840)^2} = \frac{\pi}{16} \times 80 \times d^3$$

$$d = 56 \text{ mm}$$

According to maximum normal stress theory

$$M_e = \frac{1}{2} \left((k_m \times M) + \sqrt{(k_m \times M)^2 + (k_t \times T)^2} \right) = \frac{\pi}{32} \times \sigma_b \times d^3$$

$$M_e = \frac{1}{2} \left((1.5 \times 1246440) + \sqrt{(1.5 \times 1246440)^2 + (1.0 \times 1725840)^2} \right) = \frac{\pi}{32} \times 160 \times d^3$$

$$d = 52 \text{ mm}$$

Note: Self weight of the drum = (volume of flange + volume of drum) 7860

$$W_d = \left\{ \left(2 \times \frac{\pi}{4} \times (0.522)^2 \times 0.015 \right) + \left(\left(\frac{\pi}{4} \times ((0.414)^2 - (0.384)^2) \right) \times 0.314 \right) \right\} \times 7860 = 950 \text{ N}$$

Design of motor shaft

While designing the shafts on the basis of strength, the following cases may be considered:

1. Shafts subjected to twisting moment only.
2. Shafts subjected to bending moment only.
3. Shafts subjected to combined twisting and bending moment.

Numerical on design of shaft

A solid shaft is transmitting 3.5476 KW at 140 rpm having 4.154 m long is supported in pillow block bearings at its ends and carries a two wire rope drum having self weight of 950 N each and it is located at 415 mm from end bearing on both side. Shaft is made of 45C8 having yield tensile stress of 480 MPa. Rope drum A & B carried a load of 7990 N each and having 3.324 m distance between them. Take factor of safety is 5. Determine the diameter of shaft on the basis of twisting moment, bending moment and combined twisting & bending moment. Take $k_m = k_b = 1.5$ and $k_t = 1$.

Given data :

$$P = 3.5476 \text{ KW} = 3547.6 \text{ W}$$

$$N = 140 \text{ rpm}$$

$$L_s = 4.154 \text{ m} = 4154 \text{ mm}$$

$$W_d = 950 \text{ N}$$

$$L = 415 \text{ mm}$$

Carbon steel designation : 45C8 (0.45 % C & 0.8 % Mn)

$$\sigma_{yt} = 480 \text{ MPa}$$

$$F = 7990 \text{ N}$$

$$L_1 = 3.324 \text{ m} = 3324 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{FOS} = 5$$

Now,

$$\sigma_t = \sigma_b = \frac{\sigma_{yt}}{5} = \frac{480}{5} = 96 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_t}{2} = \frac{96}{2} = 48 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\sigma_{cr} = \sigma_c = 2\sigma_t = 2 \times 96 = 192 \text{ MPa}$$

As per ASME code : $k_m = k_b = 1.5$ and $k_t = 1.0$ for rotating shaft (gradually applied or steady load).

$$\text{Total load acting on the shaft (W)} = F + W_d = 7990 + 950 = 8940 \text{ N}$$

Shaft is subjected to twisting moment only

Solution :

Power transmitted is given by

$$P = \frac{2\pi NT}{60}$$

$$3547.6 = \frac{2 \times \pi \times 140 \times T}{60}$$

$$\text{Torque transmitted (T)} = 242 \text{ Nm} = 242000 \text{ Nmm}$$

The shaft is designed on the basis of strength from the torsion equation,

$$T = \frac{\pi}{16} \times \tau \times d^3$$

$$242000 = \frac{\pi}{16} \times 48 \times d^3$$

$$d = 30 \text{ mm}$$

Shaft is subjected to bending moment only

Fig 7 Motor shaft carrying two drums

Solution:

$$\sum F_y = 0$$

$$R_A + R_D = 17880$$

Taking moment about point A to find reaction force, $\sum M_A = 0$

$$8940 \times 415 + 8940 \times 3739 - R_D \times 4154 = 0$$

$$R_D = 8940 \text{ N} \ \& \ R_A = 8940 \text{ N}$$

Bending moment at A, B, C & D are as follows :

$$M_A = 0$$

$$M_B = R_A \times L = 8940 \times 415 = 3710100 \text{ Nmm}$$

$$M_C = R_D \times L = 8940 \times 415 = 3710100 \text{ Nmm}$$

$$M_D = 0$$

$$M = \text{Maximum bending moment} = 3710100 \text{ Nmm}$$

$$M = \frac{\pi}{32} \times \sigma_b \times d^3$$

$$3710100 = \frac{\pi}{32} \times 96 \times d^3$$

$$d = 74 \text{ mm}$$

Shaft is subjected to combined twisting and bending moment

Fig 8 Motor shaft and its vertical load diagram

Solution :

Power transmitted by the shaft

$$P = \frac{2\pi NT}{60}$$

$$3547.6 = \frac{2 \times \pi \times 140 \times T}{60}$$

Torque transmitted (T) = 242 Nm = 242000 Nmm

Free body diagram of the shaft carrying two load (W) with two end bearings 4.154 m as shown in above figure 4.5.

Considering vertical load diagram,

$$\sum F_y = 0$$

$$R_A - 8940 - 8940 + R_D = 0$$

$$R_A + R_D = 17880$$

Taking moment about point A to find reaction force,

$$\sum M_A = 0$$

$$8940 \times 415 + 8940 \times 3739 - R_D \times 4154 = 0$$

$$R_D = 8940 \text{ N} \ \& \ R_A = 8940 \text{ N}$$

Bending moment at point B, $M_B = R_A \times L = 8940 \times 415 = 3710100 \text{ Nmm}$

Bending moment at point C, $M_C = R_D \times L = 8940 \times 415 = 3710100 \text{ Nmm}$

Therefore, maximum bending moment = $M = 3710100 \text{ Nmm}$

As the shaft is subjected to combined twisting and bending moment

According to maximum shear stress theory

Equivalent twisting moment is given by,

$$T_e = \sqrt{(k_m \times M)^2 + (k_t \times T)^2} = \frac{\pi}{16} \times \tau \times d^3$$

$$\sqrt{(1.5 \times 3710100)^2 + (1.0 \times 242000)^2} = \frac{\pi}{16} \times 48 \times d^3$$

$$d = 84 \text{ mm}$$

According to maximum normal stress theory

Equivalent bending moment is given by,

$$M_e = \frac{1}{2} \left((k_m \times M) + \sqrt{(k_m \times M)^2 + (k_t \times T)^2} \right) = \frac{\pi}{32} \times \sigma_b \times d^3$$

$$M_e = \frac{1}{2} \left((1.5 \times 3710100) + \sqrt{(1.5 \times 3710100)^2 + (1.0 \times 242000)^2} \right) = \frac{\pi}{32} \times 96 \times d^3$$

$$d = 84 \text{ mm}$$

Table 9 Summary of shaft design

Design of components	Cases of strength	Diameter (mm)
Rope drum shaft	Maximum shear stress theory	56
	Maximum normal stress theory	52
Motor shaft	Twisting moment	30
	Bending moment	74
	Maximum shear stress theory	84
	Maximum normal stress theory	84

We taken the same diameter of shaft for rope drum and motor for better operation and selected larger value for diameter of shaft due to safety point of view. Hence,

Diameter of shaft (d) = 84 mm

Step 2 : Calculation of weight of shaft

Quantity : 01

Material : Carbon Steel (45C8)

Component details

Shape/Section : Solid circular

Diameter : 0.084 m

Length : 4.154 m

$$\text{Volume of shaft} = \frac{\pi}{4} (0.084)^2 \times 4.154 = 0.023 \text{ m}^3$$

$$\text{Mass of shaft} = \text{Density} \times \text{Volume} = 7850 \times 0.023$$

Mass of motor shaft = 180.55 kg
Weight = 1771.1955 N = 1.7711955 KN

V. Fabrication Model

Fig 9 Fabrication Model

VI. Finite Element Analysis

We have done Finite Element Analysis on two static structure i.e. platform and main frame.

Table 10 Physical and mechanical properties of mild steel

Properties	Units	Values
Density (ρ)	kg/m ³	7860
Ultimate tensile strength (σ_{ut})	MPa	440
Yield strength (σ_y)	MPa	370
Young's modulus (E)	GPa	210
Shear modulus (G)	GPa	80
Bulk modulus (K)	GPa	178

6.1 Finite Element Analysis of Platform

6.1.1 Platform – Mesh Model

Fig 10 Mesh model of platform

Meshing is the process of breakdown the object in small shapes to proper define the physical shape from that we can do analysis particular broken down parts by selecting them. Meshing is a common term used for preprocessing phase of Finite Element Analysis (FEA). In meshing the minimum elements across the thickness are 5 to achieve desired accuracy or to get precise results. The mesh influences the accuracy, convergence and speed of the solution.

Table 11 Nodes and elements of platform

Bodies	Active Bodies	Nodes	Elements
22	22	35243	21577

6.1.2 Platform – Fixed Support

Fig 11 Fixed support of platform

Wire rope is fixed to slider with the help of wire rope clamp so this is fixed support for platform from which load is to be lift.

6.1.3 Platform – Loading Condition

Fig 12 Loading condition of platform

Load applied is distributed equally over a platform given in above picture. Analysis of platform is done for 898 kg/cm² (88 MPa) which acts pressure on platform while lifting operation.

6.1.4 Platform – Total Deformation

Fig 13 Total deformation of platform

Deformation is increased at the middle portion of the platform which is 6004.5 mm. Maximum deformation – 7720.1 mm and minimum deformation – 0.

6.1.5 Platform – Equivalent Stress

Fig 14 Equivalent stress of platform

Stress is pointed on platform and it increased at the middle portion of platform which is $1.8934e5$ MPa. Maximum stress – $3.4082e5$ MPa and minimum stress – 0.

6.1.6 Platform – Equivalent Elastic Strain

Fig 15 Equivalent elastic strain of platform

Maximum elastic strain is pointed on the middle of platform as shown in fig 7.6 and the value detected is 0.97871. Maximum strain – 1.7617 and minimum strain – 0.

6.1.7 Platform – Safety Factor

Fig 16 Safety factor of platform

Minimum safety factor is pointed on platform which is 0.0010856 and maximum is detected at the guardrail pipe which is 15. The guardrail is subjected to impact load so safety factor should be high at this portion.

6.2 Finite Element Analysis of Main Frame

6.2.1 Main Frame – Mesh Model

Fig 17 Mesh model of main frame

Table 12 Nodes and elements of main frame

Bodies	Active Bodies	Nodes	Elements
1	1	24129	12302

6.2.2 Main Frame – Fixed Support

Fig 18 Fixed support of main frame

Fixed Support legs are to be fixed at this fixed support portion which make stability to loading and unloading operation.

6.2.3 Main Frame – Loading Condition

Fig 19 Loading condition of main frame

6.2.4 Main Frame – Total Deformation

Fig 20 Total deformation of main frame

Maximum deformation is pointed at upper column which is 15.657 mm and it decreased towards the base and motor stand components. Maximum and minimum deformation is 17.614 mm and 0 respectively.

6.2.5 Main Frame – Equivalent Stress

Fig 21 Equivalent stress of main frame

Stress found out on the main frame is minimum. The maximum value of stress is 3588.6 MPa and minimum value is 0.13788 MPa.

6.2.6 Main Frame – Equivalent Elastic Strain

Fig 22 Equivalent elastic strain of main frame

Elastic strain found out maximum at near to welding portion of base and column as shown in fig 7.13. Maximum strain = 0.018409 and Minimum strain = 4.2162e-6.

6.2.7 Main Frame – Safety Factor

Fig 23 Safety factor of main frame

Maximum safety factor = 15

Minimum safety factor = 0.1031

Table 13 Summary of FEA result

Sl. No.	Parameters	Units	Static structures	
			Platform	Main frame
1.	Material	-	Mild steel	Mild steel
2.	Load applied	kg	898	898
3.	Total deformation	mm	7720.1	17.614
4.	Equivalent stress	MPa	3.4082e5	3588.6
5.	Equivalent elastic strain	mm/mm	1.7617	0.018409
6.	Safety factor	-	15	15

VII. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

7.1 Result

We have successfully designed and developed the loading and unloading platform (mechanical lift) for two wheeler. Also we successfully carried out Finite Element Analysis on about that we have designed. We fabricated the model of this project. The experiment and testing was successfully done by keeping dead weight of 100 kg on platform.

We further discussed about the other alternative mechanism or components which could be added to make the mechanical lift more effective in future which could lead to ease of operation.

7.2 Advantages

- Operational Safety : There is no chance of any incident while loading and unloading operation because of proper platform guardrail is provided to mechanical lift.
- Precision : This loading and unloading platform allows the exact positioning because of automated system.
- Productivity : The production rate of loading and unloading of bike is very high.
- Noise : It has no any mechanical linkages so it is free from noise.

- Flexible : It is easily possible to remove the complete motor-drum assembly so it can be easily refitted for longer lifting capacity.
- Cycle time : Time required to loading and unloading operation is less than other system.
- Ergonomics : This mechanical lifting system reduces the fatigue and lowers the risk of injury while heavy lifting.
- Efficiency : Efficiency of the mechanical lift is high in operational manner. Maximum load can lift with minimum efforts and time which is only achieved by gear motor system.
- Maintenance : There is requirement of less maintenance compared to other lifting devices.

7.3 Limitations

- This mechanical lift requires the electric supply. It can not operate without electricity.
- It is difficult to move one place to another because of more weight. It is not easy to portable.

7.4 Applications

- It is used in maintenance of huge machines in industries like manufacturing, automotive, aerospace, energy and transportation.
- It is suitable for feeding raw materials into the manufacturing equipments.
- It can be also used at construction site especially in indoors works like overhead welding, bricklaying and for pouring concrete.
- It plays an integral role when it comes to transporting, delivering and storing pallets and other goods.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

8.1 Conclusion

The loading and unloading platform is designed to lift heavy loads like bike to different heights using motor drum assembly. The material is used in this project which has maximum durability strength. The outcomes of the mechanical lift design meets the objective of the project.

In design section, the lift calculation is done successfully where the force acting on the components and various stresses in the system were calculated. 3D CAD drawing also made.

In this project, we concluded that the mechanical lift is able to carried out the loading and unloading operation in minimum time period which resulting high productivity and low operational cost rather than existing manual technology. Further the labour cost could be deducted.

8.2 Future Scope

We can use height level type of sensors with proper limit switches to achieve the desired height automatically without the use of LT control. We can try to operate loading and unloading operation on DC power source with the help of solar power. It can be make hydraulically operated sliding ramp which allow to move in forward and backward direction.

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